

Organic Pesticides. Part V*. Synthesis of Certain Fluorodiaryl Sulphonates and Hydroxydiaryl Sulphones

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Several fluorodiaryl sulphonates and hydroxydiaryl sulphones, derived from *p*-fluorophenol and *p*-cresol, have been prepared as potential pest-control chemicals.

In view of the insecticidal and fungicidal properties of Ovotran (I) and Sulphenone (II) and consequent screening of the activity of a large number of their structural analogues (Metcalf, "Organic Insecticides", p. 197; Szabo and Oswald, *Hung. Tech. Abst.*, 1955, 7, No. 1; *Chem. Abst.*, 1957, 51, 14593; Keller *et al.*, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1957, 50, 141; Frear, "Chemistry of Pesticides", p. 29; Dutch Pat. 81/1956; *Chem. Abst.*, 1959, 53, 3588), we have now synthesised several fluoro analogues of Ovotran (I) and converted them to the corresponding hydroxydiaryl sulphones of type (III), expecting that a combination of toxic phenolic function with Ar-SO₂-Ar moiety in the latter might enhance their pesticidal activity.

Although non-fluoro compounds of type (III) have been prepared by several workers (Simons *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 485; Amin and Desai, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 181; Sen and Roy, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 687; Balliah *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 391) very little work has been done on analogous fluorine compounds. Certain fluorobenzyl phenyl sulphones have, however, been patented by Boots Pure Drug Co. (B.P. 792,045 1958) as acaricides.

In this communication we report the preparation of eleven diaryl sulphonates (eight from *p*-fluorophenol and three from *p*-cresol) by the method of Sen and Roy (*loc. cit.*) by the interaction of aryl sulphonyl chlorides and appropriate phenol in acetone-alkali solution. *p*-Fluorophenol has been obtained from *p*-anisidine by the Balz-Schiemann reaction. The aryl sulphonyl chlorides have been prepared by the chlorosulphonation of the appropriate hydrocarbon by following the method of Huntress and Carten (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 511). The sulphonates have been rearranged by the Fries reaction at 130-40° (Amin and Desai, *loc. cit.*) to yield the corresponding hydroxydiaryl sulphones.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Fluoroanisole was prepared by the method of English *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 350) from *p*-anisidine (60 g.); yield 29 g. (47.5%). Its b.p. corresponds to that previously recorded.

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TABLE I

No.	Hydrocarbon.	Aryl sulphonyl chlorides.		Sulphonamide.	Aryl sulphonamides.		Formula.	% Sulphur.	
		Sulphonyl chloride.	M.P./B.P.		Obs.	Lit.		Obs.	Lit.
1.	Chlorobenzene	4-Chlorobenzene-	51-52°	4-Chlorobenzene-	142°	142-43°	$C_6H_4O_2NClS$	16.02	16.71
2.	Fluorobenzene	4-Fluorobenzene-	32-33°	4-Fluorobenzene-	124°	124-25°	$C_6H_4O_2NF_2S$	17.46	18.28
3.	<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene	2, 5-Dichlorobenzene-	35-36°	2, 5-Dichlorobenzene-	178-80°	180°	$C_6H_2O_2NC_2H_4S$	13.62	14.16
4.	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	2, 5-Dibromobenzene-	70-71°	2, 5-Dibromobenzene-	194°	194-95°	$C_6H_2O_2NBr_2S$	9.66	10.16
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromofluorobenzene	2-Bromo-5-fluorobenzene-	62-63°	2-Bromo-5-fluorobenzene-	137-36°	..	$C_6H_3O_2NBrFS$	11.98	12.59
6.	<i>p</i> -Fluorotoluene	2-Methyl-5-fluorobenzene-	155-58°/50 mm	2-Methyl-5-fluorobenzene-	139°	140-41°	$C_7H_5O_2NF_2S$	16.10	16.93
7.	α -Fluoronaphthalene	4-Fluoronaphthalene-	85-87°	4-Fluoronaphthalene-	205°	206°	$C_{10}H_7O_2NF_2S$	13.72	14.22

p-Fluorophenol was obtained by demethylation of *p*-fluoroanisole (28 g.); yield 13 g. (52%), b.p. 185-87°. Finger *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1959, 81, 94) report b.p. 185-86°.

Fluorobenzene was prepared by the Balz-Schiemann reaction (Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 609) from aniline (46.5 g.); yield 19 g. (36.6%), b.p. 82-83.5°. Heilbron and Bunbury ("Dictionary of Organic Compounds", p. 548) report b.p. 85.2°.

p-Bromofluorobenzene was prepared by the above method from *p*-bromoaniline (21.5 g.); yield 15 g. (68.7%), b.p. 150-52°. Heilbron and Bunbury (*ibid.*, p. 549) report b.p. 151.6-51.9°/755 mm.

α -Fluoronaphthalene was obtained by the above method from α -naphthylamine (25 g.); yield 13 g. (50.9%), b.p. 63-65°/5 mm. Heilbron and Bunbury (*ibid.*, p. 554) report b.p. 80°/11 mm.

Aryl sulphonyl chlorides were prepared by the method of Huntress and Carten (*loc. cit.*). The hydrocarbon (10 g.), dissolved in chloroform (50 c.c.), was chlorosulphonated at 0-5° with chlorosulphonic acid (50 g.). The contents after half an hour were poured over crushed ice. The chloroform layer separating was removed and the aryl sulphonyl chloride was isolated (solid or liquid). In some cases, chlorosulphonation was incomplete in cold and hence refluxing from 30 to 90 minutes was felt desirable. The aryl sulphonyl chlorides thus prepared were characterised as sulphonamides.

Aryl sulphonamides were prepared by the method of Huntress and Carten (*loc. cit.*). The aryl sulphonyl chloride (2 g.) was boiled for 30-40 minutes with strong ammonia (20 c.c.) and the mixture poured into cold water; the precipitated sulphonamide was isolated as usual and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The aryl sulphonyl chlorides and their corresponding sulphonamides are listed in Table I.

TABLE II

4-Fluorophenyl aryl sulphonates.

No.	Aryl.	M.P./B.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	4'-Methylphenyl	56-57°	81.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ FS	11.52	12.03
2.	4'-Chlorophenyl	101-02°	72.4	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ ClFS	11.20	11.17
3.	4'-Fluorophenyl	74-75°	63.5	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ F ₂ S	11.18	11.85
4.	2',5'-Dichlorophenyl	240-42°/40-50 mm	56.0	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ FS	9.28	9.97
5.	2',5'-Dibromophenyl	41-42°	52.0	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ Br ₂ FS	7.17	7.80
6.	2'-Bromo-5'-fluorophenyl	180-81°/30-35	49.3	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ BrF ₂ S	8.61	9.17
7.	2'-Methyl-5'-fluorophenyl	205°/2-3	52.7	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ F ₂ S	10.92	11.27
8.	4'-Fluoronaphthyl	65°	67.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ F ₂ S	9.53	10.00

Diaryl sulphonates were prepared by following the method of Sen and Roy (*loc. cit.*). To an ice-cold solution of acetone, containing aryl sulphonyl chloride (1.1M) and phenol (1M), was added a 10% aqueous NaOH solution in excess with frequent shaking. The sulphonates slowly settled down as solid or liquid except in a few cases where keeping overnight was necessary. These were washed till free of alkali and either recrystallised from aqueous ethanol or distilled under reduced pressure. The sulphonates obtained are recorded in Tables II and III.

TABLE III

4-Methylphenyl aryl sulphonates.

No.	Aryl.	M.P./B.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	4'-Fluorophenyl	85-86°	56.4	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ FS	11.70	12.03
2.	2'-Methyl-5'-fluorophenyl	170-72°/30-35 mm	68.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ FS	10.80	11.43
3.	4'-Fluoronaphthyl	59-60°	60.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ FS	9.83	10.13

Hydroxydiaryl Sulphonates.—A mixture of diaryl sulphonate (1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5M) was heated in an oil bath at 130-40° for 2 to 3 hours. The *o*-hydroxysulphonates were isolated and purified in the usual manner. Analytical data, m.p., and yields of the compounds synthesised are recorded in Tables IV and V.

TABLE IV

2-Hydroxy-5-fluorophenyl aryl sulphonates.

No.	Aryl.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	4'-Methylphenyl	45°	39.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ FS	11.63	12.03
2.	4'-Chlorophenyl	126-27°	44.4	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ ClFS	10.85	11.17
3.	4'-Fluorophenyl	65-66°	43.0	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ F ₂ S	11.08	11.85
4.	2',5'-Dichlorophenyl	84-85°	28.0	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₂ FS	10.02	9.97
5.	2',5'-Dibromophenyl	74-75°	16.2	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ Br ₂ FS	7.31	7.80
6.	2'-Bromo-5'-fluorophenyl	103°	28.3	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ BrF ₂ S	8.72	9.17
7.	2'-Methyl-5'-fluorophenyl	92-93°	49.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ F ₂ S	10.63	11.27
8.	4'-Fluoronaphthyl	101-102°	10.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ F ₂ S	9.40	10.00

TABLE V

2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl aryl sulphonates.

No.	Aryl.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	4'-Fluorophenyl	72-73°	26.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ FS	11.50	12.03
2.	2'-Methyl-5'-fluorophenyl	110°	27.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ FS	10.86	11.43
3.	4'-Fluoronaphthyl	104-05°	13.5	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ FS	9.54	10.13

The pesticidal activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be communicated in due course.

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